

METHODOLOGY FOR THE USE OF VISUAL TECHNICAL MEANS IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article is about the relevance of technical tools, their use in the lesson procedure, the improvement of the quality and efficiency of the lesson with activities such as expanding the musical ability, worldview, imagination and freethinking of students.

Keywords: interactive education, problem Education, Project Education, game-through learning, creative education, Eustric education, ICT education

We know that the year 2023 was named "year of attention and quality education to man" with the participation of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In his speeches, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev expressed this opinion - "when Will there be attention to a person? Education, education, education and once again education. I have been paying close attention to these issues six years ago and talking a lot about our education since day one. If there is education, if there is knowledge, the quality will change. Without education, attention does not change if quality does not change"¹.

Indeed, if there is education, if there is quality, if different methods and technologies are studied, if familiar with foreign experiments, there will be quality, there will be a change. If the opposite is the case, the education will face tanazul.

At the same time, a lot of demands are made from the teacher of music culture in Judah now. One of these is the retraining and professional development, the widespread use of modern pedagogical, information communication technologies in the course Process, Practical and inovational scientific research, the high level of educational process using modern forms and methods, electronic information resources.

Today, the most optimal way to increase the effectiveness of music culture lessons is to organize classes using interactive techniques. After all, interactive methods carry out the course process in the interaction and interaction of students. Interactive education is based on the organization of a joint, interaction-based movement in the process of a music lesson on the path of mastering theoretical knowledge, skills, qualifications and certain artistic

¹ <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/> "O'zbekistonda 2023 – yil "Insonga e'tibor va sifatli ta;lim yili"deb e'lon qilindi" 20/12/2022

aesthetic qualities of students. As you know, traditional musical education is based mainly on explanation, listening to music, literacy and mutual question and answer, and, naturally, the basis of the conversation was musical theoretical information. However, the main source of information was the musical – theoretical knowledge and artistic performance of the teacher, in the process of which he was the leader. At the main time of the lesson, he sought to verbally deliver his musical knowledge to students. Activity in the process is inherent only to the teacher, and students are only listeners in this situation, and when learning songs, students continue to repeat the teacher's performance. The main task of the students was to listen to the teacher, sing in the necessary places, respond in retaliation to what the teacher said when he addressed them with questions, speak only when he was allowed.

Today it is clearly noticeable that the possibilities of the interactive method in the practice of musical education are wider than the previous, traditional educational possibilities. But maintaining work in interactive techniques does not mean that the teacher abandons traditional methods, but is able to organize the content of the lesson in mutual activity, cooperation, solidarity.

Interactive learning has the following techniques;

1. Problem learning is an improved teaching technology. In this education, students are formed such skills and abilities as creative research, the promotion of certain hypotheses, the substantiation of results, the arrival of certain conclusions.

The first ideas of this type of education were based by the American psychologist and pedagogue John Dewey (1859 – 1952), who in 1894 founded the Experimental School in Chicago, where teaching is carried out not according to the curriculum, but on the basis of play and work.

John Dewey defined the following areas as the basis of problematic education:

Priority principles include social, constructive, artistic expressiveness, research.

It used tools in Qui to organize education in the indicated areas.

1. Word, works of art, technical devices
2. Game, labor.

There are many aphasias that add to this education. In this, none of the readers is left aside, in the process of discussion of the dispute, an opinion, understanding of music is formed by the readers, encouraging their opinion to be free and to himymize the thought, each side draws certain conclusions, with the help of active discussion, confidence and worldview expand to each other.

The teaching process includes handouts, cards, questionnaires, etc. used by the teacher. At the same time, it will be more beautiful if inovational methods are used on the basis of this education.

For example, taking the method "Assesment", this method of education is aimed at assessing the level of knowledge of students, checking, mastering performance and practical skills. Through this technique, the cognitive activity of the learners is diagnosed and evaluated in different directions (test, practical skills, exercise of behavioral situations, comparative analysis, determination of simtoms).

Procedure for the implementation of the method: - it is recommended to use the assesments in the course of the lesson in an individual form for the purpose of studying the existing level of knowledge of the student, outlining new information, assessing the level of assimilation of the subject or information, as well as self-assessment. It is also possible to include additional assignments in the assesment, based on the creative approach of the teacher as well as the goals of the topic.²

2. Project Education-forms in students such activities as the emergence of a desire to seek, find, thinking, critical thinking, allows you to eliminate cognitive gaps. In doing so, it is necessary for the teacher to introduce what is required, a new form and method, modern technalogies. In the course of the lesson, individual self - development of methods, the ability to find information, develop communication skills, make it possible to identify talented and talented students.

Also, students perform special tasks with the help of independent work.

These are;

1. Oral
2. Written
3. Frontal
4. Group

Returning to the organization of project activities

1. In order to organize independent work on the project, it is important to consider the following functions.
2. Make sure all independent activities are planned in advance
3. Doing serious work on the content part
4. Information is important in a systematic HUD
5. Periodic self-control

² Buxoro davlat universiteti dotsenti, pedagogika fanlar nomzodi Xodjayev B.Q, B. Mustafoyev "Musiqa o'qitish metodikasi" Buxoro - 2021

In order to improve the efficiency of Project technology and intensive training, it is necessary to provide certain pedagogic conditions

1. Positive motivation among students
2. Clearly define goals and objectives, clarify ways to solve them
3. Report version of the teacher, its scope, form and delivery time
4. Selection of consultative care, selection of evaluation criteria
3. Educational passing through the game – the game of students is diverse according to its content, feature, organization. Divided into creative and rule games. Creative game-the readers themselves come up with. And in principle, the teachers themselves come up with. Rule games include quid ones: didactic game, action game, musical game, ermak are divided into games.

In the process of learning through the game, students are entertained, their activities such as music literacy, performance of rhythmic movements develop.

4. Creative education-the fact that both the teacher and the student are creative is one of the education of the present day.

5. Eviristic education-is formed on the basis of the work that students do on their own, creating something directly under the active workplace of the teacher. The name of this method “eviristic” comes from the word “research” method. For example, the teacher himself forms the problem and involves its partial solution with the help of students. Students are encouraged to speak, reason, compare, compare, prove, reflect.

6. ICT education-this includes computer, audio, kalonka and others. It is also used in a wide range of digital technologies, multimedia audio applications and more. Great attention should be paid to the development of the ability of Independent Education in students.

Summing up, music provides such opportunities as being able to work quickly and easily as a result of the increase in the number of information technologies used in pedagogical activities, as well as being able to use them correctly on lesson topics. An independent education based on the active use of modern music computer technologies, of course, should also be known to a music teacher. The development of information delivery tools opens up a wide range of possibilities for working in an interactive mode and the effective use of interdisciplinary complex educational technologies.

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